

ASSESSMENT OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE HEALTH OF EARLY CHILDREN.

Tajieva Z.B.

PhD. Head of the Department of Pediatrics and Higher Nursing of the
Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy

Yuldasheva L.O.

Rajabova D.O.

Student of Urganch Branch of Tashkent Medical Academy.

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The purpose of scientific work. Study of factors affecting the health of early childhood. Materials and styles. Health conditions of 200 early-aged children were studied. The object of the study is children who were treated from July 2021 to December 2021 at the pediatric department of the Urganch branch clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy. Results. There were 200 children in total, 110 girls and 130 boys. According to the received data, the morbidity rate among these children was higher than 200 and made 326 (165.6%). The relatively low rate of general morbidity is the reason why not all diseases are recorded in outpatient cards. According to the information obtained using the questionnaire, 43% of parents try to treat their child without consulting a doctor. Among the examined children, according to the application, it can be seen that the incidence is most often recorded in children under 1 year of age. After 2 years of the child's life, the morbidity has a tendency to decrease, and it has increased slightly in 4-5 years. This can be explained as the result of increased attention of medical staff, patronage, and medical examinations in the first year of a child's life and in the next 4-5 years before school. According to the appeal of children, among the indicators of morbidity, according to the composition and degree, diseases of the respiratory system are in the first place (80%). Diseases of the respiratory system among girls are 44.2%, and among boys 55.8% ($r^{0.05}$). It can be seen that girls have a higher adaptive system than boys. Diseases of the respiratory system have different indicators at different ages. Most cases occur in children under 1 year of age, due to the fact that their respiratory system is not yet mature. Obstructive bronchitis (62.5%), acute simple bronchitis (15.5%) and other diseases (22%) are the main causes of respiratory system diseases. 12% of obstructive bronchitis is relapsing. The main cause of these diseases (76%) was found to be atopy, despite the fact that 68% of these children had already received antibiotics for treatment. The relatively high prevalence of chronic bronchitis, angina, and flu in children under the age of 5 is noteworthy, as these diseases increase the risk of developing chronic broncho-pulmonary diseases. Summary. Thus, in the structure of morbidity in children under 3 years of age, respiratory system diseases are high, and there is a high probability of becoming a chronic form. Doctors and pediatricians should pay serious attention to children's diseases of the respiratory system.